

THE IMPLEMENTATION OF CRIME PREVENTION PLANS, PROGRAMS, AND ACTIVITIES (CPPPA) IN THE EYES OF PHILIPPINE NATIONAL POLICE (PNP) PERSONNEL

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The Implementation of Crime Prevention Plans, Programs, And Activities (CPPPA) in the Eyes of Philippine National Police (PNP) Personnel

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Abstract

This study sought to provide a comprehensive exploration of the implementation of crime prevention plans, programs, and activities (CPPPA) by Philippine National Police (PNP) personnel, with a specific focus on four individuals from the Tacurong City Police Office. Purposive sampling was used to select the participants of the study. Additionally, utilizing a multiple case study approach within the qualitative research framework, the investigation identified three central themes: experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights gained during CPPPA implementation. Within the theme of experiences, the study brought to light three sub-themes. Despite encountering challenges and difficulties in the implementation process, PNP personnel derived happiness and fulfillment from their involvement in community activities. Notably, the study underscored the significance of community partnerships as a crucial element for effective crime prevention efforts. Transitioning to the challenges faced, three sub-themes emerged. Mistrust from certain community segments posed obstacles, hindering the efforts of PNP personnel. Additionally, the lack of support in specific instances presented challenges to the successful implementation of CPPPA. Furthermore, issues related to self-image impacted the effectiveness of crime prevention initiatives. In terms of insights, the study uncovered three sub-themes. Effective communication was highlighted as a pivotal factor for successful CPPPA implementation. The emphasis on adhering to orders and protocols emerged as a key consideration for ensuring the effectiveness of crime prevention efforts.

Keywords: *criminal justice education, crime prevention plans, CPPA, PNP, multiple case, philippines*

Introduction

"But the main problem in any community plagued by crime is not the punishment of the offenders, but prevention of the young from being trained to commit crime."-Du Bois

This quote emphasizes that while punishing criminals is essential, it is not the primary solution to reducing crime in a community. The chief problem in a community afflicted by crime lies in preventing young individuals from being trained or influenced to engage in criminal activities in the first place. Indeed, rather than solely focusing on punitive measures, the notion of preventing crime at its source is grounded in the understanding that criminal behavior often stems from social, economic, and environmental factors.

Implementing crime prevention plans, programs, and activities is crucial in safeguarding communities and reducing crime rates worldwide. However, this undertaking is fraught with challenges from diverse socioeconomic, cultural, and institutional contexts across different regions and countries. Resource constraints pose a significant hurdle, particularly in low- and middle-income nations where funding for crime prevention initiatives may be limited. Additionally, socio-political instability, corruption, and weak governance undermine efforts to address the causes of crime and foster community resilience. Emerging threats like cybercrime and online radicalization further complicate traditional crime prevention strategies, necessitating continuous adaptation and innovation (Peden, 2022).

Additionally, it is signifying that most cities and municipalities, not just in the Philippines, are facing the same problem in implementing laws related to crime prevention. The burden is always on the shoulders of law enforcement. How would they penetrate those laws that must be effective in crime prevention? Nevertheless, these laws will be void and null because they will only be pushed through with the community's help. Thus, it raises an important point about the collective responsibility in crime prevention in the Philippines and many cities and municipalities worldwide. The effectiveness of laws and law enforcement efforts in crime prevention heavily relies on active participation and cooperation from the community they serve (Lim et al., 2020).

Moreover, by addressing their various causes, crime prevention tactics, and procedures aim to lessen the crimes happening and their potentially detrimental impacts on people and society, including fear of crime. The Philippines constantly examines these issues and attempts to launch initiatives that support sector-specific programs and projects with an emphasis on at-risk youth groups and the prevention of reoffending, offering advisory services for the development and implementation of regional and national strategies and action plans, and promoting interventions based on information gained from victimization surveys and crime statistics (Walker & Archbold, 2018).

Likewise, crime prevention is a community responsibility; it is always the community that has the most significant responsibility in the implementation of laws related to crime prevention, plans, and activities because they will always be the front line of the environment. Without them, crime will never be reported to the police station, and it will never serve any justice that might be served to the victim. The community, for now, is well informed with new laws that will help law enforcement implement, plan, and acquire activities that

are vital in preventing crime in the community. Thus, this will be an excellent point for the law enforcement body to smoothly solve and implement with the help of civilians in their respective societies (Miller, 2019; Welsh, 2019).

Furthermore, the recent bombing incident on May 26, 2022, at Tacurong City, Sultan Kudarat, has resulted in a more substantial commitment by all concerned to devote effort and time to the essential task of seeking peace and order in the said urban area. Through this incident, the Philippine National Police of Tacurong was challenged in terms of problems encountered in criminal activities and the prevention of the successful commission of crimes (Dy, 2022).

As a criminology instructor, it is a critical juncture in the fight against crime. The rising tide of criminal activities demands a robust and comprehensive crime prevention plan, programs, and activities. Every passing moment without decisive action poses a greater risk to the safety and security of our neighborhoods. Time is of the essence, and we cannot afford to delay any longer. The urgency to bolster crime prevention efforts stems from the unwavering commitment to protect communities and secure a better future for future generations. They call upon government agencies, community leaders, law enforcement personnel, and concerned citizens to rally together, unite in purpose, and implement effective crime prevention measures without hesitation.

The urgency of conducting this study is overstated. It is crucial to assess the implementation of crime prevention plans, programs, and activities from the perspective of the Philippine National Police (PNP). Understanding the PNP's viewpoint is crucial to enhancing public safety, allocating resources effectively, evaluating effectiveness, fostering community engagement, improving policies, sharing best practices, promoting transparency, and facilitating long-term planning. Through this study, stakeholders can work collaboratively to develop evidence-based crime prevention strategies for a safer Philippines.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the implementation of crime prevention plans, programs, and activities (CPPPA) in the eyes of PNP Personnel, particularly in the SOCCSKSARGEN police station. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the questions:

1. How do the participants describe their experiences as PNP personnel in implementing the CPPPA?
2. What are the similarities and dissimilarities among the cases in terms of coping, experiences, and insights?

Methodology

This section explains the research methodology used in this study. It includes the researcher's role, study subjects, data collection, data analysis, methodologies, credibility, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

This study used the qualitative research methodology utilizing multiple case study approaches. It aimed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the challenges faced by the personnel of the Tacurong City and General Santos City Police Office, specifically in their efforts to implement crime prevention plans, programs, and activities. By conducting an in-depth investigation, this study aimed to shed light on the specific problems encountered by the PNP personnel and offer valuable insights into potential solutions for enhancing their crime prevention initiatives.

Among all scientific procedures, qualitative research methods are most likely the most ancient. The goal of the qualitative observations of the world around the ancient Greek philosophers was to comprehend and explain what they saw. A range of methods for methodically analyzing statistical or numerical data to study social phenomena is known as quantitative research design. Because of this, quantitative research is measurement-based and presupposes that the phenomena being examined can be measured. Its objectives are to validate the measurements and look for patterns and linkages in the data (Hennink et al., 2020).

Additionally, the methodological approach of qualitative research centers on the subjective experiences, meanings, and interpretations of events to investigate and comprehend them in their natural environments. Qualitative research depends on non-numerical data like observations, interviews, and textual analysis, in contrast to quantitative research, which prioritizes numerical data and statistical analysis. Qualitative researchers frequently use various techniques, such as focus groups, participant observation, document analysis, interviews, and case studies, to obtain rich and comprehensive data. In qualitative research, descriptive and narrative data are usually collected, enabling researchers to understand the viewpoints, attitudes, and behaviors of the participants (Muzari et al., 2022).

Moreover, the primary objective of qualitative research is to gain a sophisticated understanding of intricate social phenomena, along with developing hypotheses and new insights. It is beneficial when examining subjects based on context, which is subjective or calls for a close analysis of people's experiences and perspectives. Qualitative research presentations commonly include detailed descriptions, themes, and narratives to offer a more profound comprehension of the research topic. These results can guide the creation of theories, policies, and additional quantitative research (Williams, 2019).

Likewise, a qualitative multiple case study is a type of research design in which several instances are examined along with qualitative research methods. It entails examining several bounded systems or cases in-depth to comprehend a phenomenon or research subject fully. Researchers usually choose instances for a qualitative multiple-case study that offer various viewpoints or variants pertinent to

the research question. Individuals, groups, organizations, communities, or any other clearly defined unit of analysis can be considered in these circumstances. The objective is to analyze every example separately and then compare and contrast them in order to find trends, themes, and similarities among the cases (Cardano, 2020).

On the other hand, the case study method is an invaluable research approach that allows for exploring real-life, contemporary bounded systems or multiple bounded systems over time. This method involves conducting detailed and in-depth data collection from various sources of information, enabling the researcher to understand the case(s) under investigation comprehensively. The ultimate goal of a case study is to provide a thorough case description and identify key case themes, which offer valuable insights and contribute to the existing body of knowledge in the field (Williams, 2019).

Additionally, the qualitative case study method must be better understood despite being frequently employed. It might be challenging to demonstrate scientific completeness and justify any conclusions that arise from qualitative case studies because of competing epistemological theories and their inherent complexity. Additionally, case studies serve two purposes: they can be studies of a single unit or studies of a larger group of units. A case study may seek to reach an illustrative or confirmable conclusion. These problems need to be clarified in case study design and will continue to do so as they are part of the organization (Hancock et al., 2021).

Moreover, the qualitative case study method provides researchers with valuable tools to comprehensively understand phenomena within their respective contexts. When applied appropriately, this method offers several advantages for studying science, evaluating programs, and developing theories and interventions. By utilizing the qualitative case study method, researchers can delve deeply into the intricacies of the research subject, capturing the richness and complexity of real-life situations. Through detailed data collection techniques such as interviews, observations, and document analysis, researchers can explore multiple facets of the phenomenon, allowing for a comprehensive view (Tomaszewski et al., 2020).

Furthermore, the approach is constructive when researching science because it allows researchers to examine participant interpretations and subjective experiences while investigating events in their natural environments. This method enables a more nuanced comprehension of the research topic, adding to the body of scientific knowledge and possibly revealing new information. The qualitative case study approach is also a good fit for program evaluation. Researchers can evaluate the efficacy, impact, and execution of programs within their particular contexts by thoroughly investigating particular cases. The approach makes it possible to pinpoint the variables that affect program results and makes it easier to thoroughly evaluate the program's advantages and disadvantages (Hancock et al., 2021).

Participants

Since this is a multiple-case study, the researcher used a purposive sampling method to pick the participants. Specifically, the research participants in this study were the four personnel-implementers: 2 personnel from Tacurong City and two from General Santos City Police Office's crime prevention plans, programs, and activities (CPPPA). An individual in-depth interview and a focus group discussion of the personnel-implementer are included because the study's primary purpose is to learn more about the participants' encounters with the problems in implementing the CPPPA. The criteria for selecting this study's participants are personnel who belonged to the Police Community Relation Group (PCRG) and are Rank of Police corporal to higher rank. Lastly, they have been assigned in Police Community Relation Group for the past three years.

Inclusion Criteria. The researcher utilized the purposive sampling method. Since the participants needed are police officers in charge of the Police Community Relation Group (PCRG), the researcher set the inclusion criteria: male or female residing within Tacurong City and General Santos City, must be a graduate of criminology course, must possess a qualification of a professional police officer, with rank of police corporal to a higher rank and lastly three years assigned in Police Community Relation Group and must be the implementer of CPPPA.

Exclusion Criteria. The scope of this study was limited to police officers with experience in CPPPA. Police officers who had not been involved in such activities were excluded from the study. Furthermore, the study focused on officers currently employed in law enforcement agencies and under the age of 60. Retired officers were not considered for this research. By focusing on police officers with relevant experience and who were currently employed, this study aimed to gain a deeper understanding of the experiences, insights, and challenges faced by those most directly involved in implementing CPPPA.

Withdrawal Criteria. Throughout the research, participants were reminded of their freedom to leave the study at any time without facing any repercussions. Thus, the study ensured that participants knew their rights and could easily withdraw from the study if they were uncomfortable or decided they were no longer ready to participate. It was not necessary for them to give a cause for leaving.

Data Collection

The semi-structured interview guide was employed to conduct focus groups and in-depth interviews. The researcher first created research questions that a validator verified. To ensure the study was carried out ethically, the researcher obtained approval from the Ethics Research Committee (ERC) after the research questions have been validated. When the committee approved the study, the researcher sought permission from the Dean and the Philippine National Police (PNP) stations in Tacurong City and General Santos

City Police Regional Office XII (GSCPO XII). After obtaining authorization, the researcher needed to ask those willing to engage in the study for their participation and requested an informed consent form. The researcher then conducted interviews to collect data for the study when the participants agreed to participate and approve of the study.

Additionally, the researcher was responsible for meeting the participants. He discussed the procedures and guidelines for data gathering. At the interview, the researcher read the questions to the participants twice, and more if necessary. To avoid any confusion, the researcher read the questions aloud. Participants had plenty of time to think over their answers. Furthermore, the researcher verbally summarized the participants' responses to each question to ensure that the participants' answers were understood.

Furthermore, to maintain confidentiality, the researcher addressed the participants throughout the interview using their given code names or pseudonyms, such as participant 1, participant 2, participant 3, and participant 4. In addition, the entire interview was recorded on a smartphone. After the interview, the researcher transcribed the audio recordings and showed the interview transcript to the participants in order to accurately reflect their ideas. The numerical and verbal result were also shown. Participants were also able to edit the transcript. After they had agreed to their transcript, the participants signed a form verifying their interview data. All of the questions in the interview guide led to a description and understanding of the implementation of CPPPA in their police station. The interview guide questions aided comprehension.

Data Analysis

The recorded responses were translated into English through the help of a professional English teacher. The researcher translated the meaning of the original in a form that was almost identical in English. After the translation, the translated version was presented to the research participants for checking (Jackson & Bazeley, 2019).

The researcher strictly recorded all the data coming from the participants. The researcher assigned a code to something for classification or identification in coding. Thus, this helped to locate these critical data quickly. Categorizing this was the researcher's process and technique to analyze the situation based on the vitality of the information and data. Formulating themes served as the room and division of the information given by the participants through analyzing and interpreting the data collected. Lastly, after the data and information were gathered, the researcher reported all the crucial details of the solution to the problem, as indicated in this study (Busetto et al., 2020).

Ethical Considerations

In this qualitative investigation, an important ethical aspect carries significant implications. These issues and concerns mainly stem from the methodology employed during the study. Ethical considerations revolved around properly executing the research and safeguarding confidentiality and anonymity. The RMMC Ethics and Review Committee's ethical guidelines were scrupulously followed during the study, particularly concerning the population and data involved, encompassing aspects beyond those explicitly mentioned.

Voluntary Participation. The option to participate was given to the participants without mentioning a plan for consequences, compensation, or loss of benefits. Therefore, when the study's goal and benefits were communicated to the participants, their rights to add to the body of knowledge were carefully examined and expected. None of the study's subjects were forced to participate. People have the option to stop participating in the poll if they start to feel uncomfortable.

Privacy and confidentiality. The Data Privacy Act of 2012 protects this essential human right and ensured that participants' private rights were not infringed upon without their informed consent. One method utilized in this quantitative study to preserve privacy and confidentiality was to allow participants to exclude their names from the survey questionnaire. By suppressing the informants' personal information, such as their age, gender, occupation, and health conditions, confidentiality and privacy were also maintained.

Informed consent process. Given the limitations of the investigation, the potential research volunteers were adequately informed about the study's goals, procedures, and advantages. The participant's affirmative response demonstrated that the request for their involvement was voluntary. The informed consent form required participants to sign to indicate that they freely chose to participate in the study. The participant's identities were not listed on the survey form, and their responses were kept private.

Recruitment. The purpose of the study's inclusion was explained to the participants. The researcher presented the study's goal to the participants so they would know what to expect from it and could view its main points. In addition to the letter, the researcher explained the background of the study and its importance.

Risks. If the benefit-risk ratio is acceptable and positive, research should be done. It is equally important for this investigation that the participants are shielded from severe damage. The well-being of the participants was given priority throughout the study. Furthermore, the participants suffered no harm because their identities would be kept private. Their safety and security were first and foremost. The researcher will ensure the participants are emotionally, physically, and socially prepared.

Benefits. The study's participants had the opportunity to learn essential lessons that could help them create programs and initiatives that effectively prevent crimes and advance public safety. It is crucial to emphasize the great effort to guarantee that the study's

participants were not harmed and that their participation helped advance related research projects. The study's most significant gain was the development of critical facts and insights that could guide future efforts to enhance public safety and reduce crime.

Plagiarism. No traces or indications of misinterpretation of someone else's work were found in the study. It was checked for plagiarism using tools like Grammarly. Understand the value of sustaining good moral character and integrity, which are connected to moral virtues and ideals. In order to ensure the validity of the research paper, it was essential to have a thorough comprehension of plagiarism.

Fabrication. The report had no hint or evidence that the work had been intentionally misinterpreted. There was no fabrication of data and findings or deliberate presentation of false conclusions. Thus, theories related to information and other inferential concepts were employed and integrated.

Falsification. The study did not purposefully misrepresent the work for theoretical expectations and had no evidence of overclaiming or exaggeration. Additionally, this study did not adhere to manipulating the data, which would have involved formulating statements or disregarding important details, maneuvering materials, tools, or methodologies that could mislead others.

Conflict of Interest (COI). There was no indication of a conflict of interest in the study, like disclosure of COI or circumstances where professional judgment on the principal appeal is required. It is similar to the monetary academic advantages or recognitions and tends to influence participants' welfare or the research's validity. In addition, the researcher, who had no authority or control over the subjects, forced them to participate in the study.

Deceit. The study did not mislead the participants about any possible danger. The rights of the participants must be humongously protected in any investigation, especially if they have attained higher education. Thus, reasonable and well-balanced principles were followed.

Permission from Organization/Location. The adherence to the study protocols and obtained approval from various authorities, including the RMMC-ERC committee, the Police Precinct Commanders in General Santos City, Tacurong City, and the Tupi Police Office in Region XII. The approval process required formal letters and an endorsement from the Police Regional Director.

Results

This qualitative multiple-case research aimed to learn more about the participants' experiences, difficulties, and epiphanies as PNP employees while carrying out crime prevention strategies, programs, and activities (CPPPA). This study also included the outcomes of five interviews. Each case participant was disguised with a pseudonym to protect the chosen instances' identities and privacy. The researcher employed name codes based on their frequently used connected symbols.

Description of Participants

Case 1—Ford Ranger was a male police officer from Tacurong City. He had been with the Philippine National Police for over eight years and was exclusively assigned to the Police Office's Crime Prevention Plans, Programs, and Activities (CPPPA).

Case 2—Dagger was male police personnel from General Santos City. He had been in the Philippine National Police for over ten years and was assigned to the Police Office's Crime Prevention Plans, Programs, and Activities (CPPPA).

Case 3—Compass was a male police officer from Tacurong City. He had been with the Philippine National Police for over 12 years and was assigned to the Police Office's Crime Prevention Plans, Programs, and Activities (CPPPA).

Case 4—Trigger One was a male police officer from General Santos City. He had been with the Philippine National Police for over seven years and was exclusively assigned to the Police Office's Crime Prevention Plans, Programs, and Activities (CPPPA).

The participants were asked questions during the interview, followed by clarifying or probing questions. The critical inquiry was whether PNP personnel at the SOCCSKSARGEN police station were satisfied with how the Crime Prevention Plan, Programs, and Activities (CPPPA) was implemented. This kind of open-ended grand tour inquiry allowed people to share their tales without being constrained. Sub-questions included in the semi-structured interview guide were also asked to elicit particular experiences. The researchers gave each informant a guarantee of anonymity and non-disclosure. As a consequence, the disclosures from the study's five examples are consistent with one another.

The four participants in the case study were Ford Ranger, Dagger, Compass, and Trigger One (all pseudonyms). The following chapters present detailed descriptions of the five cases.

3.1. CASE 1 - FORD RANGER

Ford Ranger is a male police officer from Tacurong City. He had been with the Philippine National Police for over eight years and is exclusively assigned to the Police Office's Crime Prevention Plans, Programs, and Activities (CPPPA).

Experiences of PNP Personnel in the Implementation of Crime Prevention Plans, Programs and Activities (CPPPA)

Ford Ranger was asked about his experiences as PNP personnel in implementing the CPPPA. He provided insights into his duties and

responsibilities within this framework. His response shed light on both his experiences and his approach to handling the responsibilities entrusted to him. He answered:

Ang aking karanasan sa pagpapatupad ng CPPPA bilang isang PNP personnel ay halo-halo, may bahagi na pagod, takot ngunit masaya. Hinahawakan ko ito nang may pagmamalaki at dignidad dahil ito ang napili kong career. (Participant 1 lines 4-6)

The experience implementing the CPPPA as a PNP personnel is mixed. There is a part that is scared but happy. Handle it with pride and dignity because it is the chosen career (Participant 1, lines 4-6).

When questioned about the implementation of CPPPA, he lauded it as the optimal approach to cultivating solid ties between the community and law enforcement. He affirmed his wholehearted endorsement of the program, underscoring his unwavering dedication to contributing to its success, driven by love and pride. His commitment transcends mere necessity, as he stands ready to support its implementation, embodying a spirit of service and dedication.

Ang pagpapatupad ng CPPPA ay ang pinakamahusay na paraan kung paano nabuo ang relasyon ng komunidad at pulisya. Yes, sinusupportahan ko ito, sa paraang kung kailangan nila ako o hindi, tutulongan ko silang ipatupad ito nang may pagmamahal at pagmamalaki. (Participant 1 lines 9-11)

Implementing CPPPA is the best way to mold the relationship between the community and the police. Yes, support it so that whether they need it or not, I will help them implement it with love and pride (Participant 1 lines 9-11).

He revealed that he has been a PNP personnel for approximately eight years. Regarding the impact of CPPPA implementation on his work, he stated that it does not affect his duties, as the primary objective of their organization is to uphold peace and order within the community.

Mga 8 years na. No, ang pag implement ng CPPPA ay hindi nakakaapekto sa aking trabaho dahil ang main purpose ng aming organisasyon is to maintain peace and order sa komunidad (Participant 1 lines 11-14).

It has been eight years. The implementation of CPPPA cannot affect the work because the organization's primary purpose is to maintain peace and order in society (Participant 1 lines 11-14).

When asked about his most unforgettable experience encountered as he implemented the CPPPA, he recounted the invaluable assistance of the community in promoting crime prevention, which bridged the gap between residents and the police. This experience shaped him, instilling a sense of responsibility and a commitment to being a positive role model within the community.

And di ko makakalimutang karanasan ay ang pagtulong ng komunidad sa amin sa pagtataguyod ng crime prevention sa lipunan na kung saan ang gap between sa komunidad at sa pulis ay nawala. It molds me as individual na maging mas responsible at mabuting halimbawa sa komunidad (Participant 1 lines 19-22)

The most unforgettable experience was seeing the community help us promote crime prevention in society, bridging the gap between the community and the police. Thus, it molds the individual to become more responsible and sets an excellent example for the community (Participant 1 lines 19-22).

He highlighted the effectiveness of CPPPA implementation, emphasizing its primary objective of fostering a positive relationship between PNP personnel and the community. This initiative encourages individuals to abstain from criminal involvement and aids the PNP in crime prevention efforts within society.

Napakabisa ng pagpapatupad ng CPPPA dahil ang unang pangunahing layunin nito ay maisulong ang relasyon ng mga tauhan ng PNP at komunidad na maghihikayat sa kanila na huwag masangkot sa anumang krimen at makatulong din sa PNP na maiwasan ang krimen sa kanilang lipunan. (Participant 1 lines 24-27)

The implementation of CPPPA is very effective because its primary goal is to promote a positive relationship between PNP personnel and the community, encouraging them to refrain from involvement in any criminal activities. Additionally, it helps the PNP prevent crime in society (Participant 1, lines 24-27).

Challenges encountered by the PNP personnel in implementing the CPPPA

When asked about the challenges encountered in implementing CPPPA and how he addressed them, he emphasized the difficulty of gaining community support and participation due to eroded trust in PNP personnel. He tackled this issue by persuading the community that CPPPA would aid in rebuilding trust in law enforcement and advancing peace within their society.

Ang mga hamon na naranasan sa pagpapatupad ng CPPPA ay ang pagkuha ng suporta at partisipasyon ng komunidad dahil nawawala na ang tiwala ng komunidad sa mga tauhan ng PNP. Hinahawakan ko ito sa pamamagitan ng paghikayat sa kanila na ang CPPPA na ito ay tutulong sa kanila na ibalik ang tiwala sa mga tauhan ng PNP at tulungan silang isulong ang kapayapaan sa kanilang lipunan (Participant 1 lines 30-34)

The challenges experienced in implementing CPPPA involve gaining the support and participation of the community, as the trust in

PNP personnel needs to be recovered. Handle it by encouraging them that CPPPA would help restore trust in the PNP personnel and promote peace in their society (Participant 1 lines 30-34).

When queried about the personal effects of these challenges, he disclosed experiencing a decline in self-esteem stemming from the community's lack of trust. To address this, he engages in self-convincing, recognizing the significance of CPPPA in aiding the organization's efforts to curb crime in society.

Bilang indibidwal nakakaapekto ito sa akin Nagkakaroon ako ng mababang pagpapahalaga sa sarili dahil wala silang tiwala sa amin. Pinangangasiwaan ko ito sa pamamagitan ng pagkumbinsi sa aking sarili na ang CPPPA na ito ay mahalaga upang matulungan ang organisasyon na mabawasan ang mga krimen sa lipunan (Participant 1 lines 37-39)

It affects the individual. I have low self-esteem because people do not trust me. I manage it by convincing myself that this CPPPA is essential to helping the organization minimize crimes in society (Participant 1 lines 37-39).

When asked about his strategies for overcoming challenges, he highlighted the significance of self-realization and seeking support from others. These approaches proved invaluable, motivating him to continue supporting CPPPA efforts.

Ang mga strategies ay pagkakaroon ng self-realization at sa pamamagitan din ng tulong ng iba. Malaking tulong ito dahil nagbigay ito sa akin ng maraming motibasyon na patuloy na suportahan ang CPPPA (Participant 1 lines 42-44)

The strategies are self-realization and also through the help of others. It is beneficial because it motivates the participant to continue supporting the CPPPA (Participant 1, lines 42-44).

When questioned about the impact of challenges in implementing CPPPA on his mental and emotional well-being as a PNP personnel, he acknowledged feeling affected as he realized the lack of public interest in supporting the program despite its potential to prevent crime. However, he clarified that these challenges did not lead to severe stress for him, as he believed it was essential for a police officer to remain motivated and resilient in fostering relationships between personnel and the community.

Ito ay naka apekto sa akin mentally at emotionally sapagkat na realize ko na although ang CPPPA ay nakakatulong sa sosyudad na maiwasan ang krimen pero ang mga tao ay hindi interesado na suportahan ito. No, hindi ito nag reresult sa severe stress dahil bilang isang police officer ay dapat motivated and keep myself strong to mold ang relasyon ng personnel at ng komunidad (Participant 1 lines 48-52).

It affected me mentally and emotionally when I realized that this CPPPA would help society prevent crime, but people are not interested in supporting it. No, it did not result in severe stress. As a police officer, I must motivate myself and keep myself strong to mold the relationship between us personnel and the community (Participant 1 lines 48-52).

When questioned about how he coped with the challenges, he explained that he relied on training programs and activities focused on implementing CPPPA effectively. He emphasized the importance of engaging in activities that involved multiple participants to enhance the implementation process.

Sa pamamagitan ng pag train at mga programa kung papaano e implement ang CPPPA. Ang mga activities na kung saan marami ang sumasali sa pag implement ng CPPPA (Participant 1 lines 55-57)

I engaged in activities by participating in multiple programs and training on implementing the CPPPA (Participant 1, lines 55-57).

Insights of PNP personnel in the implementation of Crime Prevention Plans, Programs and Activities (CPPPA)

When questioned about the insights gained as a PNP personnel in implementing CPPPA, he expressed having learned valuable lessons in handling community members and executing CPPPA effectively. One critical insight he shared was the importance of perseverance and courage in supporting CPPPA implementation efforts, highlighting the necessity for resilience in overcoming challenges.

Marami akong natutunan, kung papaano e handle ang mga tao sa komunidad at kung papaano e implement ang CPPPA. Ang insight na maibahagi ko ay ang pagkakaroon ng perseverance at courage sa pag support sa implementation ng CPPPA (Participant 1 lines 61-63).

I learned a lot about how to handle the people in the community and how to implement the CPPPA. The insight is to have the perseverance and courage to support the implementation of CPPPA (Participant 1 lines 61-63).

He shared insights on effective CPPPA implementation, emphasizing the need for full support, courage, and love. Specifically, he highlighted the importance of respectful communication with the community and setting an example of law-abiding behavior among PNP personnel.

Sa pagkakaroon ng epektibong implementasyon dapat lahat ay full support, courage at love sap ag iimplement ng CPPPA. Bilang halimbawa, maayos at respetong komunikasyon sa komunidad at pagiging isang magandang halimbawa na ang PNP personnel ay hindi violator ng batas (Participant 1 lines 66-69).

Effective implementation requires full support, courage, and love for implementing the CPPPA. We should communicate to the community with respect and become good examples that PNP personnel are not violators of the law (Participant 1 lines 66-69).

He shared his thoughts on CPPPA implementation, expressing its challenges and rewards. He believed that promoting peace and order in the community was crucial, and he aimed to inspire PNP personnel to work together with the community for more effective results.

Ang aking na realize sa pag implement ng CPPPA ay mahirap pero masaya dahil as long as we implement CPPPA ay napopromote din namin ang peace and order sa kumunidad. I will inspire them na magresulta sa mas epektibong implementasyon ng CPPPA na makakatulong sa PNP organization na mapadali ang trabaho sa tulong ng komunidad (Participant 1 lines 73-77).

(The realization is that implementing CPPPA is hard but happy because as long as we implement the CPPPA, the more we promote peace and order in the community. I will inspire them with the result of the CPPPA that effective implementation helps the PNP organization to work efficiently with the help of the community) (Participant 1 lines 73-77)

He outlined his commitment to continuing the effective implementation of CPPPA with love and courage, regardless of their duty status. He also emphasized his intention to be a positive role model for other police officers, demonstrating that their earned respect stems from supporting the CPPPA.

Palagi kong susuportahan ang pagpapatupad ng CPPPA nang may pagmamahal at tapang kahit na ako ay nasa tungkulin man o wala. Magiging mabuting halimbawa ako sa iba na ang paggalang na nakuha ko sa komunidad ay bunga ng suporta sa CPPPA (Participant 1 lines 80-82).

I will always support the implementation of CPPPA with love and courage, whether I am on duty or not. I will be an excellent example to others, and the respect I earned with the community resulted from my support in CPPPA (Participant 1 lines 80-82).

Participant 1's insights on the practical implementation of CPPPA for other police officers and stations include promoting full support and increased focus on the initiative. By doing so, they believe that peace and order will be further enhanced, and the community's feelings will be considered, which in turn assists the organization in preventing crimes.

Ibabahagi ko sa ibang opisyal ng pulisya at himpilan ng pulisya na magkaroon ng buong suporta at higit na pagtutok sa pagpapatupad ng CPPPA. Kung mas sinusupportahan natin at mas nakatuon ang ating pansin sa pagpapatupad ng CPPPA, lalo nating itinataguyod ang peace and order, nakukuha rin natin ang damdamin ng komunidad upang tulungan ang organisasyon na maiwasan ang mga krimen (Participant 1 lines 85-88)

I will share with other police officers and stations to fully support and focus on implementing CPPPA. The more we support and focus on implementing CPPPA, the more we promote peace and order. We also get the community's feelings to help the organization prevent crimes (Participant 1, lines 85-88).

Table 1. *Experiences of PNP Personnel in the Implementation of Crime Prevention Plans, Programs and Activities (CPPPA)*

<i>Clustered Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
<i>Challenges</i>	
Mixed Emotions. Commitment Despite Challenges. Long Term Service Perspective. Endorsement of CPPPA. Support and Pride. Unforgettable Positive Experiences. Community Engagement. Positive Relationship Building. Effectiveness of CPPPA.	Difficult to implement Happiness Partnership with the Community
<i>Coping</i>	
Community Distrust in PNP Personnel Efforts to Rebuild Trust. Impact on Self-Image. Difficulty in Gaining Community Support. Personal Effects of Lack of Support. Need for Self-Conviction. Impact on Self-Esteem. Coping Strategies for Self-Image. Focus on Mental and Emotional Well-Being.	Mistrust Lack of Support Self-Image
<i>Insight</i>	
Effective communication strategies. Community Involvement and Engagement Building Trust and Relationship. Adherence to laws and regulations. Setting standards and expectations.	Communication Obeying Others

Leadership and Role Modeling.
Inspiring others and motivation.
Building reputation and trustworthiness.

Good Example

3.2. CASE 2 - DAGGER

Dagger is a male police officer from General Santos City. He has been with the Philippine National Police for over ten years and is assigned to the Police Office's Crime Prevention Plans, Programs, and Activities (CPPPA).

Experiences of PNP personnel in the implementation of Crime Prevention Plans, Programs and Activities (CPPPA)

Dagger shared his challenging experiences as a PNP personnel implementing the CPPPA, highlighting the complexities arising from widespread involvement in crime within the city or region. He emphasized his approach to fulfilling his responsibilities by adhering to the PNP's mission and vision, enforcing laws impartially, and implementing them without bias, showcasing his commitment to maintaining law and order.

Ang aking karanasan sa pagimplement ng CPPPA ay hindi madali ang pagpapatupad ng programa dahil sa ilang pangyayari na maraming tao ang nasasangkot sa krimen sa lungsod o rehiyon. Hinahawakan ko ang aking mga responsibilidad bilang PNP sa pamamagitan ng pagsunod sa mission at vision ng PNP sa pamamagitan ng pagpataw ng mga batas na ibinibigay sa atin bilang miyembro ng pambansang pulisya ng Pilipinas at sa pamamagitan ng implement nito nang walang bias (Participant 2 lines 92-98).

(My experience in implementing CPPPA is that the program is challenging due to some circumstances, such as many people being involved in the city or region. I am handling my responsibilities as a PNP by following the mission and vision of the PNP by imposing the laws given to us as members of the Philippine national police and implementing them without bias). (Participant 2 lines 92-98).

When asked about his stance on implementing CPPPA, Dagger emphasized its significance in preventing crime in the city, expressing his full support for the program. He underscored his commitment to maintaining peace and order in both the city and region through the equitable enforcement of the program within the community, highlighting the importance of consistency and fairness in its implementation.

Napakahalaga ng pag implement ng CPPPA dahil pinipigilan nito ang paglitaw ng krimen sa lungsod at yes, sinusuportahan ko ang programa upang mapanatili ang peace and order sa lungsod at rehiyon sa pamamagitan ng pantay na pagpapatupad sa komunidad (Participant 2 lines 99-103).

Implementing CPPPA is very important because it prevents crime in the city. I support the program's goal of maintaining peace and order in the city and region by implementing it equally in the community (Participant 2, lines 99-103).

When questioned about his tenure as a PNP personnel and the impact of CPPPA implementation on his work, Dagger revealed his ten-year service in the force. He acknowledged the initial challenges faced during the program's rollout, citing instances where individuals, including friends, were affected by its enforcement, indicating the complexities inherent in implementing such initiatives within communities.

Ako ngayon ay 10 years na sa serbisyo sa ngayon sa unang implementasyon ng programa ay hindi madali dahil sa mga pangyayari na ang mga tao o kaibigan ay apektado sa pagpapatupad (Participant 2 lines 109-114).

I have been in the service, sofa,r, for ten years, and this was the program's first implementation. It has been challenging due to the circumstances with which those people or friends are affiliated (Participant 2, lines 104-106).

When asked about his most unforgettable experience during CPPPA implementation, Dagger recalled encounters with individuals who opposed the program due to misunderstandings. He reflected on how these experiences shaped him personally, emphasizing the challenging nature of implementing such initiatives and the time required for acceptance and adoption by community members. These insights underscore the complexities and interpersonal dynamics of enforcing CPPPA within communities.

Ang hindi ko makalilimutang karanasan sa pag implement ng CPPPA ay kapag may mga taong hindi sang-ayon sa pagpapatupad ng programa dahil sa ilang hindi pagkakaunawaan, sa magkabilang panig. It molds me bilang isang indibidwal dahil ang pagpapatupad ng nasabing programa ay hindi madali kailangan ng panahon para ipataw at maangkin ng mga kinauukulang tao sa komunidad.(Participant 2 lines 109-114).

The most unforgettable experience I encountered implementing CPPPA was when people disagreed with the program's implementation due to misunderstandings. This experience molded me as an individual because implementing the program takes work. It takes time to impose it and to be adopted by the concerned people in the community (Participant 2, lines 109-114).

When questioned about the effectiveness of CPPPA implementation, Dagger asserted that its effectiveness hinges on proper enforcement and fairness in implementation. He highlighted its efficacy in controlling the escalation of crime in the region, emphasizing the program's ability to mitigate criminal activities through consistent enforcement measures. These remarks underscore the importance of procedural integrity and equitable application in achieving desired outcomes within the community.

Ito ay epektibo in a sense na dapat itong ipataw nang maayos at dapat itong maging patas sa mga tuntunin ng pagpapatupad. mabisa ito dahil makontrol ng krimen na nagaganap sa rehiyon ang paglala dahil sa pagpapatupad ng programa (Participant 2 lines 116-119).

It is effective because it must be adequately imposed and fair in implementation. It is effective because the crime occurring in the region can control the escalation due to the program's implementation (Participant 2, lines 116-119).

Challenges encountered by the PNP personnel in implementing the CPPPA

When asked about the challenges encountered in implementing CPPPA and how he managed them, Dagger highlighted the need for coordination between the community and the police officers assigned in the municipality. He explained that this challenge stemmed from the officers' reluctance to report incidents in their areas due to fear, underscoring the importance of addressing communication barriers and fostering trust to overcome such obstacles effectively.

Ang mga hamon na nararanasan namin sa pagpapatupad ay ang kawalan ng koordinasyon sa komunidad sa mga pulis na nakatalaga sa munisipyo dahil natatakot silang mag-ulat ng ganitong insidente na nangyayari sa kanilang mga lugar. (Participant 2 lines 122-126).

The challenges we experienced in the implementation are the need for coordination between the community and the police officers assigned to the municipality because they are afraid to report incidents occurring in their areas (Participant 2 lines 122-126).

When asked about the personal impact of these challenges, Dagger expressed how they affected him. He explained that residing in an area where there is a lack of coordination between the community and police officers creates fear for him and his family, as safety, peace, and order are compromised. This response underscores the emotional toll and sense of vulnerability experienced by individuals directly affected by the challenges in CPPPA implementation.

Nakakaapekto ito sa akin bilang isang indibidwal dahil alam nating lahat na kung ikaw ay naninirahan sa lugar na iyon, ikaw at ang iyong pamilya ay natatakot sa sitwasyong maaaring mangyari, ang kaligtasan, kapayapaan at kaayusan ay maaaring makaapekto dito (Participant 2 lines 127-129).

It affects me because, as we all know, if you reside in that area, you and your family may fear any situation that can affect your safety, peace, and order (Participant 2, lines 127-129).

When questioned about his strategies to overcome the challenges, Dagger outlined his approach. He emphasized the importance of following orders and developing solutions to combat obstacles. Additionally, he highlighted the necessity for personnel to devise strategies to address challenges and understand the strategies employed by potential adversaries. This response underscores the proactive and adaptive measures Dagger took to navigate difficulties in CPPPA implementation effectively.

Ang mga strategies na ginamit ko upang malampasan ay sundin kung ano ang magiging utos at gumawa din ng ilang solusyon upang labanan ang mga hamon bilang tauhan kinakailangan na gumawa ng ilang mga strategies upang malaman din ang mga strategies ng kalaban (Participant 2 lines 132-135).

The strategies I used to surpass these were to follow whatever the order was and devise solutions to combat the challenges as personnel. It is necessary to map out some strategies and know the enemy's strategies (Participant 2, lines 132-135).

When asked about the mental and emotional impact of CPPPA implementation as a PNP personnel, Dagger shared his experience. He explained that initially, it affected his mindset and emotions due to the differences between PNP personnel and community members, necessitating actions to regain trust. However, he noted that this dynamic does not apply in every situation, highlighting the nuanced challenges and considerations in navigating relationships between law enforcement and the community. This response illustrates Dagger's complex interplay of emotions and responsibilities in his role.

Sa una ang pagpapatupad ng CPPPA ay nakakaapekto sa aking kaisipan at damdamin dahil magkaiba ang mga tauhan ng PNP at ang mga tao sa komunidad kailangan mong gumawa ng ilang aksyon o sundin ang gusto ng mga tao sa komunidad upang maibalik ang tiwala ng mga indibidwal na iyon. ngunit hindi sa lahat ng pagkakataon sa isang tiyak na sitwasyon lamang (Participant 2 lines 139-143)

At first, the implementation of CPPPA affected my mentality and emotions because PNP personnel and the people in the community are different. You must take action or follow the community's wants to regain their trust, but only sometimes in a particular situation (Participant 2, lines 139-143).

When asked how he coped with the challenges encountered in CPPPA implementation, Dagger shared the strategies employed by the PNP. He mentioned that the PNP conducts various activities, such as moral recovery programs, to address the challenges faced by personnel experiencing difficult situations due to their duties.

Ang mga aktibidad na aming ginagawa ay ang PNP ay nagsasagawa ng ilang mga aktibidad upang makabangon din sa mga hamon halimbawa ang moral recovery ng mga PNP personnel na nakakaranas ng masamang sitwasyon dahil sa pagganap ng kanilang mga

tungkulin bilang PNP personnel (Participant 2 lines 146-149).

The activities we engage in are that the PNP conducts several activities to recover from challenges, for example, the moral recovery of those PNP personnel who are experiencing bad situations due to performing their duties as PNP personnel (Participant 2 lines 146-149).

Insights of PNP personnel in the implementation of Crime Prevention Plans, Programs and Activities (CPPPA)

When questioned about the insights gained from implementing the CPPPA as a PNP personnel, he emphasized the importance of adhering to PNP guidelines and executing tasks diligently. His response underscored the necessity of following instructions and implementing procedures by established protocols to ensure effective program enforcement. Thus, it highlights the significance of procedural adherence and disciplined execution in achieving the objectives of CPPPA implementation within the law enforcement framework.

Ang insight na maibabahagi ko ay gawin ang anumang gawain na ibibigay at ipatupad ito alinsunod sa mga guidelines ng PNP (Participant 2 153-154).

You should complete the task given and implement it according to the PNP guidelines (Participant 2, lines 153-154).

When questioned about insights he could offer other police stations regarding the effective implementation of CPPPA, Dagger emphasized the importance of following orders and executing the program impartially for the community's benefit. He suggested conducting Police-Community Relations (PCR) activities to restore community and PNP trust.

Ang maibabahagi ko lang sa ibang istasyon sa mabisang pagpapatupad ay, sundin ang mga utos at ipatupad ang programa ng patas sa mga kinaukulan sa komunidad halimbawa, magsagawa ng PCR para maibalik ang tiwala ng komunidad sa PNP (Participant 2, lines 157-160).

The only thing I can share with other stations regarding effective implementation is to follow orders and implement the program fairly to the people in the community. For example, PCR can be conducted to give back the community's trust in the PNP (Participant 2, lines 157-160).

When asked about his realization regarding the effective implementation of CPPPA and how he plans to inspire other PNP personnel, Dagger expressed his intention to lead by example. He emphasized promoting strategies that ensure fair execution of the program, such as following orders and implementing policies impartially. Thus, it highlights his commitment to fostering a culture of transparency and accountability within the PNP, inspiring colleagues to strive for excellence in enforcing CPPPA.

Bibigyan ko sila ng inspirasyon sa pamamagitan ng pag-promote ng mga diskarte na maaaring ilapat upang maipatupad ang programa nang patas tulad ng kung ano ang nabanggit ko sa mga sumusunod na utos at ipatupad nang patas. (Participant 2 lines 164-166)

I will inspire them by promoting strategies that can be applied to implement the program fairly, like what I have mentioned, in the following orders and implementing fairly (Participant 2 lines 164-166).

When asked about his commitment to continuing the effective implementation of CPPPA and supporting other police officers, Dagger reaffirmed his dedication to fulfilling his duties as a PNP personnel. He emphasized the importance of adhering to orders given to him and fellow PNP personnel while also serving as a reminder of the duties and functions of the PNP. Thus, it reflects his proactive approach to maintaining accountability and professionalism within the organization, ensuring ongoing support for CPPPA implementation and the collective efforts of the PNP.

Palagi kong ipapatupad ang aking tungkulin bilang PNP at susundin ang utos na ibinigay sa akin at sa iba pang PNP personnel at ipa alala ang tungkulin at functions ng PNP (Participant 2 lines 169-171)

I will always uphold the PNP's duties, follow the tasks given to me and other PNP personnel, and remember the PNP's duties and functions (Participant 2 lines 169-171).

When asked to share insights with other police offices or stations regarding the effective implementation of CPPPA, Dagger emphasized the importance of adhering to correct procedures and avoiding actions that could tarnish the overall image of the PNP. His response underscores the significance of maintaining professionalism and integrity in all activities related to CPPPA enforcement, ensuring that the reputation of the PNP remains untarnished. Thus, it highlights the critical role of ethical conduct and accountability in upholding the credibility of law enforcement efforts within the community.

Ang insight na maibabahagi ko sa ibang PNP offices ay ang paglalapat ng tama at pag-iwas sa mga aksyon na maaaring magbigay ng masamang imahe sa PNP sa pangkalahatan (Participant 2 line 174-175)

I can share with other PNP offices the insight that they should apply what is right and avoid actions that can give the PNP a lousy image (Participant 2, lines 174-175).

Table 2. *Experiences, Coping and Insights of PNP Personnel in the Implementation of Crime Prevention Plans, Programs and Activities (CPPPA)*

<i>Clustered Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
<i>Experiences</i>	
Operational Challenges.	Difficult to Implement
Personal Struggles.	
Organizational Adaptation.	Happiness
Sense of Fulfillment.	
Personal Growth.	
Community Impact.	Partnership with the Community
Community Engagement.	
Trust and Collaboration.	
Empowerment and Ownership	
<i>Challenges</i>	
Lack of Coordination.	Mistrust
Emotional Impact.	
Rebuilding Trust.	Lack of Support
Reluctance to Report.	
Emotional and Mental Impact.	
Coping Mechanism.	Self-Image
Personal Impact.	
Strategies for Coping.	
Organizational Response.	
<i>Insight</i>	
Effective Communication Channels.	Communication
Community Engagement Strategy.	
Interagency Collaboration.	Obeying to others
Accountability and Responsibility.	
Leadership to Example.	
Integrity and Ethics.	Good Example
Inspiring Trust and Confidence.	

3.3. CASE 3 - COMPASS

Compass is a male police officer from Tacurong City. He has been with the Philippine National Police for over 12 years and is assigned to the Police Office's Crime Prevention Plans, Programs, and Activities (CPPPA).

Experiences of PNP personnel in the implementation of Crime Prevention Plans, Programs and Activities (CPPPA)

Compass described his experiences implementing the CPPPA as a roller coaster ride, citing challenges such as community non-cooperation that complicates program implementation. He manages his responsibilities by prioritizing tasks and maintaining a balance, relying on a structured approach with a prioritized list of actions. Thus, it highlights his strategic mindset and proactive approach to navigating the complexities of enforcing the CPPPA.

Ito ay isang roller coaster ride. Ang ilan sa aking karanasan ay ang komunidad ay hindi nakikipagtulungan at ito ay nagpapahirap sa programa na ipatupad. Pinangangasiwaan ko ang aking mga responsibilidad sa pamamagitan ng pagbabalanse ng aking mga priyoridad. Mayroon akong listahan kung ano ang unang gagawin at kung ano ang susunod (Participant 3 lines 179-182).

It was a roller coaster ride. Some of my experiences include the community, which is uncooperative, thus making the program more difficult to implement. I handle my responsibilities by balancing my priorities. I have a list of what to do first and what comes after (Participant 3, lines 179-182).

He emphasized that CPPPA serves as a platform to unite the police and community, strengthening their relationship and fostering harmonious ties. Compass pledged his commitment to supporting the program by maximizing his efforts to implement it without complaints about his duties, showcasing his dedication to the initiative's success. Thus, it reflects his proactive approach to bridging the gap between law enforcement and the community, ensuring collaborative efforts in crime prevention and maintaining peace and order.

Ang CPPPA ay magiging isa sa mga paraan upang pagsama-samahin ang pulisya at komunidad. Palalakasin ko ang kanilang ugnayan at makalikha ako ng maayos na relasyon sa isa't isa. Oo, sinusupportahan ko ang programa sa paraang gagawin ko ang aking makakaya upang maipatupad ang programa nang hindi nagrereklamo tungkol sa aking Gawain (Participant 3 line 185-188).

CPPPA will be one way to bring the police and community together. I will strengthen their bonds to create harmonious relationships with each other. Yes, I support the program by doing my best to implement it without complaining about my task (Participant 3, lines 185-188).

He revealed that he has been in service for 12 years as a PNP personnel. Regarding the impact of CPPPA implementation on his work, he asserted that it does not affect his duties as a PNP officer since their primary responsibility is to uphold peace and order in the community. Thus, it underscores his unwavering commitment to his role as a law enforcement officer, prioritizing fulfilling his duties despite the challenges posed by CPPPA implementation.

Ako ay nasa serbisyo sa loob ng 12 years. Hindi, hindi ito nakakaapekto sa aking trabaho bilang isang tauhan ng PNP dahil naibigay na sa atin ang ating pangunahing tungkulin na panatilihin ang peace and order sa komunidad. (Participant 3 line 191-193).

I have been in the service for 12 years. No, it does not affect my work as a PNP personnel because it is already given that our primary duty is to maintain peace and order in the community. (Participant 3 lines 191-193).

His most unforgettable experience implementing CPPPA was witnessing the community and the police working together seamlessly. This experience made him more friendly and open to society, highlighting the transformative impact of collaboration between law enforcement and the community.

Ang makita ang komunidad at ang pulisya na nagtatrabaho bilang isa ang aking pinaka-hindi malilimutang karanasan sa ngayon. Ito ang naghubog sa akin na maging mas palakaibigan at bukas sa lipunan (Participant 3 line 196-198).

Seeing the community and the police work as one was my most unforgettable experience so far. It has molded me to become more friendly and open to society (Participant 3, lines 196-198)

Describing the implementation of CPPA as highly effective in maintaining peace and order in the community, he emphasized its unifying effect on both the police force and the community. He likened its impact to the proverbial act of hitting two birds with one stone, highlighting its benefits.

Masasabi kong napakabisa ng pagpapatupad ng CPPPA sa mga tuntunin ng pagpapanatili ng peace and order sa komunidad. Gayundin, pinagsama nito ang pulisya at komunidad. Kaya ito ay tulad ng paghampas ng dalawang ibon sa isang bato (Participant 3 line 200-202).

Implementing CPPA is very effective in maintaining peace and order in the community. It has brought the police and community together, so it is like hitting two birds with one stone (Participant 3 lines 200-202).

Challenges encountered by the PNP personnel in implementing the CPPPA

He described the primary challenge as the populace's lack of trust in the Philippine National Police (PNP), making it challenging to foster their confidence initially. However, he addressed this by demonstrating to the people that the police force is reliable and a friend to the community, emphasizing the importance of building trust through actions.

Ang pangunahing hamon para sa akin ay ang ideya na ang PNP ay walang tiwala ng mga tao. Napakahirap palakasin ang loob nila kapag sa unang pagkakataon ay wala silang tiwala sa atin. Hinawakan ko sa pamamagitan ng pagpapatunay sa mga tao na ang pulis ay mapagkakatiwalaan at isang kaibigan sa mga tao (Participant 3 lines 205-208).

The main challenge for me is that the PNP needs the people's trust. It is not easy to encourage them when, in the first place, they do not trust us. I handled it by proving to the people that the police are trustworthy and a friend to people). (Participant 3, lines 205-208)

He shared that those challenges greatly affected his self-esteem and confidence, leading him to question his capabilities as an authority figure. However, he found resilience in the belief that, with perseverance, they could eventually earn the people's trust.

Sa totoo lang, ang mga hamong iyon ay nagpababa ng aking pagpapahalaga at tiwala sa sarili. It made me question my capability as a person in authority. Gayunpaman, nagawa kong harapin ito sa pag-iisip na balang araw, kahit papaano, makukuha natin ang tiwala ng mga tao (Participant 3 lines 211-214).

In fact, those challenges lowered my self-esteem and self-trust. They made me question my capability as an authority figure. However, managing to face them with the thought that someday, somehow, we could gain people's trust (Participant 3, lines 211-214).

He engaged in introspection, comparing his present self to who he was five years ago, which led to the realization of his positive personal growth. This newfound self-awareness instilled confidence in his ability to implement CPPPA effectively at this juncture.

Napaisip ako sa aking sarili. Kung babalikan ko kung sino ako 5 years ago at kung sino ako ngayon. That made me realize na nagbago na ako for the better. Kaya kong ipatupad ang CPPPA sa pagkakataong ito (Participant 3 lines 217-219).

I have been contemplating myself. Looking back five years ago, I have realized the change for the better and I can implement the CPPPA at this time (Participant 3, lines 217-219).

Confronting these challenges induced significant mental and emotional stress, particularly as he grappled with the realization that he could not hasten processes according to his schedule, requiring patience to cultivate trust. Nonetheless, he found solace in his duty as a police officer, understanding the imperative of maintaining personal integrity as people depended on his support.

Sa totoo lang, ito ay nagdala sa akin ng stress sa pag-iisip na hindi ko maaaring madaliin ang mga bagay ayon sa aking plano. Kailangan kong maging matiyaga upang makuha ang tiwala ng mga tao. Gayunpaman, nakaya ko ito dahil bilang isang pulis hindi ko dapat ibaba ang sarili ko dahil may mga taong nangangailangan ng tulong ko. (Participant 3 lines 223-226)

Honestly, it has caused me stress to think that I could not rush things according to my plan. I needed to be patient to gain people's trust. However, I managed it because, as a police officer, I must not bring down myself. After all, there will be people who will need my help. (Participant 3 lines 223-226)

He disclosed that his main coping strategies for the challenges involved daily learning and deepening his understanding of the program. Actively participating in webinars and diverse workshops allowed him to enrich his knowledge and skills to navigate better the hurdles he encountered.

Sa pamamagitan ng pag-aaral araw-araw at pag-aaral ng higit pa tungkol sa programa ay ang aking mga paraan upang makayanan ang mga hamon na aking kinakaharap. Dumalo ako sa mga webinar at iba't ibang mga workshop upang mapahusay ang aking mga natutunan (Participant 3 lines 229-231).

Learning daily and studying more about the program are my ways of coping with my challenges. I have attended webinars and workshops to enhance my learning (Participant 3, lines 229-231).

Insights of PNP personnel in the implementation of Crime Prevention Plans, Programs and Activities (CPPPA)

In discussing the insights, he gained as a PNP personnel in implementing the CPPPA, he highlighted the significance of socializing and understanding the community. He further emphasized to his fellow police officers the importance of perseverance and patience for successfully executing the program.

Mas natutunan ko ang pakikisalamuha at pag-unawa sa mga tao sa paligid mo. Ibabahagi ko sa aking mga kasamahang opisyal ng pulisya na ang tiyaga at pasensya ang susi upang matagumpay na maipatupad ang programa (Participant 3 lines 235-237).

I learned about socializing and understanding people. I have shared with the co-police officers that perseverance and patience are essential to successfully implementing the program (Participant 3, lines 235-237).

He was asked about insights he could share with other police stations regarding implementing CPPPA effectively. He emphasized the necessity of collective effort, stating that police personnel cannot achieve success alone. Stressing the importance of wholehearted support from leadership, he cited hands-on involvement in the program and avoiding reliance solely on lower-ranking officers as beneficial strategies for implementation.

Ibinabahagi ko na hindi ito kayang gawin ng mga tauhan ng pulisya nang mag-isa. Ang buong pusong suporta mula sa mga pinuno ay makakatulong nang malaki sa pagpapatupad. Halimbawa, ang pagiging hands-on sa programa at hindi umaasa lamang sa mas mababang mga opisyal ay makikinabang sa pagpapatupad (Participant 3 lines 240-243).

The Police personnel cannot do it alone. A whole-hearted support from the heads would greatly help the implementation. For example, being hands-on with the program and not relying solely on the lower rank officers would benefit the implementation (Participant 3 lines 240-243).

When asked about his realization regarding the effective implementation of the CPPPA and his plan to inspire other PNP personnel, he described the process as exhausting and rewarding, citing the challenges encountered and the resulting positive outcomes. He emphasized that the program's success would serve as a source of inspiration for fellow PNP personnel, motivating them to strive even harder in their endeavors.

Nakakapagod pero sulit. Nakakapagod dahil sa mga hamon at sulit dahil sa kinalabasan. Ang positibong resulta ng programa ay magiging inspirasyon ng iba pang mga tauhan ng PNP na magsikap pa (Participant 3 lines 247-249).

It was exhausting but worth it. Exhausting because of the challenges and worth it because of the outcome. The positive result from the program would greatly inspire other PNP personnel to strive more (Participant 3 lines 247-249).

When asked about his approach to implementing CPPPA effectively and supporting fellow police officers, he expressed his determination to uphold the program's standards regardless of his duty status. He emphasized his readiness to contribute significantly by perpetuating the positive actions of their organization, demonstrating a steadfast commitment to the program's success and the collective improvement of their efforts.

Sa tungkulin man o hindi, patuloy kong itataas ang pagpapatupad ng programa. Malaki ang maitutulong ko sa pagpapatuloy ng mga kabutihang ginagawa ng ating organisasyon (Participant 3 lines 253-254).

On duty or not, I would continue to improve the program's implementation. I would greatly help by continuing our organization's good deeds (Participant 3, lines 253-254).

When asked about insights he could share with other police offices or stations regarding effective CPPPA implementation, he

underscored the importance of police officers offering full support to the program. He emphasized that successful implementation was facilitated by officers' collaborative efforts, highlighting teamwork's significance in achieving program goals.

Ang mga opisyal ng pulisya ay dapat magkaroon ng buong suporta sa programa dahil mas maraming mga opisyal na nagtutulungan, mas makakamit natin ang matagumpay na pagpapatupad ng programa. (Participant 3 lines 257-259)

Police officers must fully support the program because the more officers working together, the more successful the program's implementation will be (Participant 3 lines 257-259).

Table 3. *Experience, Challenges and Insights of PNP Personnel in the Implementation of Crime Prevention Plans, Programs and Activities (CPPPA)*

<i>Cluetered Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
<i>Experiences</i>	
Community Non-cooperation and Program. Implementation Challenges.	Difficult to Implement
Strategic Management and Prioritization. Adaptation and Proactive Approach.	
Fulfillment in Successful Implementation. Personal Growth and Positive Impact.	
Community Satisfaction and Well-Being. Unity building and Relationship Strengthening.	Happiness
Transformative Impact of Collaboration. Dual Benefits and Positive Outcomes.	Partnership with the Community
<i>Challenges</i>	
Lack of Community Trust ain the PNP. Impact on Self-Perception.	Mistrust
Resilience and Confidence Building. Absence of External Assistance.	Lack of Support
Internal Struggles and Coping Mechanisms. Duty and Integrity.	
Impact of Challenges on Self-Esteem. Recognition of Personal Growth.	Self-Image
Commitment to Personal Development.	
<i>Insight</i>	
Significance of Socializing and Understanding. Emphasis on Collective Effort.	Communication
Support from Leadership. Determination to Uphold Standards.	Obeying the Others
Collaboration and Teamwork. Leadership Support and Influence.	
Personal Dedication and Sacrifice. Inspirational Leadership.	Good Example
Impact of Positive Results.	

3.4. CASE 4 - TRIGGER ONE

Trigger One is a male police officer from General Santos City. He has been with the Philippine National Police for over seven years and is exclusively assigned to the Police Office's Crime Prevention Plans, Programs, and Activities (CPPPA).

Experiences of PNP personnel in the implementation of Crime Prevention Plans, Programs and Activities (CPPPA)

Trigger One was asked about his experiences as a PNP personnel implementing the CPPPA and how he handles his responsibilities. He described his experience as fulfilling, citing the reduction of crimes and the evident support from the community. Emphasizing the integral role of police officers in serving communities nationwide, he highlighted the duty to serve as a cornerstone of their profession.

Ang aking karanasan sa pagpapatupad ng CPPPA ay medyo masaya dahil nakakabawas ito ng mga krimen at nakikita rin ang suporta ng komunidad. Bilang isang pulis, ang ating buhay ay itinayo sa mga komunidad sa buong bansa, at tayo ay dapat paglingkurang (Participant 3 lines 263-266).

My experience in implementing the CPPPA has been quite happy because it lessens crimes, and the community supports it. As police officers, our lives are built into communities nationwide, and we are meant to serve (Participant 4, lines 263-266).

When asked about the implementation of CPPPA and his support for the program, he highlighted its importance as a strategy to address nationwide crises. Affirming his support, he described providing a more equitable social experience and facilitating community learning as his contributions to the program's objectives.

Ang pagpapatupad ng CPPPA ay isa sa mga istrategiya na ginagamit upang malampasan ang krisis sa buong bansa. Oo, sinuportahan ko ang programa sa paraang nagbigay ako ng mas pantay na karanasan sa lipunan at pagkatuto sa komunidad (Participant 4 lines 269-271).

Implementing CPPPA is one strategy used to overcome crises around the country. I supported the program by providing the community with a more equal social and learning experience (Participant 4, lines 269-271).

When asked about his tenure as a PNP personnel and the impact of CPPPA implementation on his work, he revealed seven years of service without significant disruption to his duties. Emphasizing the continuity of his primary role to serve the people and provide peace wherever they reside, he indicated that this responsibility remains unchanged despite CPPPA implementation.

7 years na akong nagsilbi sa PNP at hindi ito nakakaapekto sa ating mga trabaho sa pagpapatupad ng CPPPA, dahil ang pangunahing tungkulin ng aking sinumpaang tungkulin ay paglilingkuran ang mga tao at bigyan sila ng kapayapaan kung saan sila umalis (Participant 4 lines 274-276)

I have served in the PNP for seven years now, and no, the implementation of CPPPA does not affect our jobs because the central role of my sworn duty is to serve the people and to give them peace where they live (Participant 4 lines 274-276).

When asked about his most unforgettable experience while implementing the CPPPA, he highlighted facing myriad challenges, particularly concerning community support. Reflecting on this experience, he emphasized how it molded him as an individual, underscoring his unwavering commitment to serving the country and its people despite such obstacles.

Ang hindi ko malilimutang karanasan na aking hinarap ay ang mga napakaraming hamon na kung paano natin ipapatupad ang CPPPA na ito kung hindi ito sinusupportahan ng komunidad. Ang hulma nito sa akin bilang indibidwal na kahit ang karanasang ito ay hindi magiging hadlang sa paglilingkod sa bayan at sa mga tao (Participant 4 lines 279-282).

The unforgettable experience I've faced is the myriad challenges of implementing this CPPPA, in the reality that the community needs to support it. It has molded me as an individual so that even this experience will not hinder my service to the country and the people (Participant 4, lines 279-282).

When asked about the effectiveness of CPPPA implementation, he affirmed its efficacy, citing how police officers better represent the communities they serve. He emphasized the more profound understanding of community needs and concerns resulting from this representation, highlighting the collaborative efforts to make communities safer and more robust.

Ang pagpapatupad ng CPPPA ay epektibo dahil mas kinakatawan ng ating mga pulis ang mga komunidad na ating pinaglilingkuran, mas naiintindihan natin ang kanilang mga pangangailangan at alalahanin at mas mahusay tayong nagtutulungan upang gawing mas ligtas at mas malakas ang mga komunidad (Participant 4 lines 284-289).

The implementation of CPPPA is effective because the more our police officers represent the communities we serve, the more we understand their needs and concerns, and the better we work together to make communities safer and more robust (Participant 4, lines 284-289).

Challenges Encountered by the PNP Personnel In implementing the CPPPA

He discussed encountering significant challenges while implementing CPPPA, particularly regarding community support. Despite these obstacles, he emphasized perseverance and committed to continuous promotion until community backing was secured. His response underscores a determined effort to navigate challenges and maintain momentum toward achieving program goals despite adversities.

Ang isang malaking karanasan na hinaharap ko ay kung paano ipatupad ang CPPPA kung hindi nila ito sinusupportahan. Hinahawakan ko ng buong tiyaga na kahit hindi nila sinusupportahan ito ay patuloy tayong magsusulong at hindi titigil hangga't hindi natin nakukuha ang kanilang suporta (Participant 4 lines 290-292).

A significant experience I have encountered in implementing CPPPA was the need for them to support it. I handle this with perseverance, and even though they are not supporting it, we will continue to promote it and will not quit until we get their support (Participant 4 lines 290-292).

He faced the challenges with a warm heart, believing in reciprocity. He emphasized that helping others benefits them and contributes to one's sense of happiness. This outlook enabled him to navigate the difficulties with resilience and a positive mindset.

Hinarap ko ang hamon with a warm heart dahil naniniwala ako na kung ano ang ibinibigay ko ay kung ano din ang nakukuha ko. Ang pagtulong sa iba ay hindi lamang nakikinabang sa kanila, ngunit makakatulong din ito sa iyong pakiramdam na mas masaya ang iyong sarili (Participant 4 lines 295-297).

They faced the challenge with warm hearts because what they gave was what they got. Helping others benefits them and can make you happier (Participant 4 lines 295-297).

He attributed his success in overcoming challenges to divine assistance and his organization's support. The aid of the Almighty was

invaluable, instilling a belief that with divine help, nothing is insurmountable. Additionally, he highlighted the effectiveness of teamwork within their organization, emphasizing that they could implement the CPPPA effectively through collective effort.

Sa tulong ng Almighty at sa tulong din ng organisasyon. Napakalaking tulong nito dahil ang tulong ng makapangyarihan ay walang imposible at gayundin ang pangkatang gawain ay epektibo nating ipinatutupad ang CPPPA (Participant 4 lines 300-302).

It is beneficial to have the aid of the Almighty and the organization's help because nothing is impossible. With teamwork, we can effectively implement the CPPPA (Participant 4 lines 300-302).

He acknowledged being affected mentally and emotionally by the realization that the CPPPA could benefit society in crime prevention despite the public's lack of interest and support. However, he clarified that this did not result in significant stress, as he understood the necessity of maintaining resilience as a police officer to implement the CPPPA effectively. This perspective helped him cope with the challenges and remain steadfast in his duty to serve and protect the community.

Naapektuhan ako mentally at emotionally sa pamamagitan ng pag-unawa na ang CPPPA na ito ay makakatulong sa lipunan upang maiwasan ang krimen ngunit ang mga tao ay hindi interesado na suportahan ito. Hindi, hindi ito nagreresulta ng matinding stress dahil bilang isang pulis kailangan kong maging matatag para epektibong maipatupad ang CPPPA (Participant 4 lines 306-309)

It affected me mentally and emotionally because I realized that this CPPPA will help society prevent crime, but people are not interested in supporting it. No, it did not result in severe stress because, as a police officer, I need to become vital to effectively implement the CPPPA (Participant 4 lines 306-309).

He described coping with the challenges by maintaining faith in the effective implementation of the CPPPA and trusting in his fellow PNP personnel and the organization. This belief in their collective ability gave him strength and resilience to overcome the obstacles encountered during the implementation process. Through this mindset, he navigated the challenges with confidence and determination.

Sa pamamagitan ng paniniwalang epektibo nating ipatutupad ang CPPPA at paniniwala rin sa aking mga kasamahang tauhan ng PNP at sa organisasyon (Participant 4 lines 312-313).

We will effectively implement the CPPPA and believe in the PNP personnel and the organization (Participant 4, lines 312-313).

Insights of PNP personnel in the implementation of Crime Prevention Plans, Programs and Activities (CPPPA)

He shared insights gained from implementing CPPPA, emphasizing that its effective implementation can reduce crime in society. His takeaway message underscores the importance of loving one's work and serving as a positive role model for others, highlighting the significance of personal dedication and exemplary behavior in law enforcement.

Natutunan ko sa pagpapatupad ng CPPPA na kung mabisa ang ipatutupad ay mababawasan natin ang krimen na nangyari sa ating lipunan. Ang insight na ibabahagi ko ay dapat nating mahalín ang ating trabaho at dapat maging mabuting halimbawa sa iba (Participant 4 lines 317-319).

In implementing the CPPPA, I have learned that if it is effectively implemented, we can reduce crime in our society. I will share that we must love our work and be an excellent example to others (Participant 4, lines 317-319).

In response to the inquiry about insights for other police stations regarding effective CPPPA implementation, he emphasized the importance of aligning with the program's goals and mission. He stressed that the implementation should aim to reduce crime rates and foster peace within the community.

Dapat nating ituon ang mga layunin at misyon ng CPPPA na ang pagpapatupad nito ay makakabawas sa krimen at makapagsusulong ng kapayapaan (Participant 4 lines 322-323).

We must focus on the goals and mission of the CPPPA, that implementing it will reduce crime and we can promote peace (Participant 4 lines 322-323).

In response to queries regarding his realization upon committing to effectively implement the CPPPA and inspire fellow PNP personnel to strive harder, he elucidated the clarity achieved in defining their duties, extending beyond apprehending suspects to actively reducing societal crime through CPPPA implementation. He emphasized the overarching goal of crime reduction in their community. He outlined a vision to inspire collective efforts to achieve this objective, fostering a safer environment for all.

Malinaw naming tinukoy kung ano ang aming trabaho na hindi namin palaging huhulihin ang suspek ngunit layunin din namin na mabawasan ang krimen na nangyari sa aming lipunan sa pamamagitan ng pagpapatupad ng CPPPA at mabawasan ang mga hinaharap na krimen (Participant 4 lines 327-329)

We clearly defined our work: We will not always arrest suspects, but we also aim to reduce crime in our society by implementing CPPPA and preventing future crimes (Participant 4 lines 327-329).

In response to inquiries about how he plans to sustain effective CPPPA implementation and support his fellow police officers, he

underscored the importance of executing his duties diligently and precisely as a police officer. He expressed his commitment to aiding his colleagues by setting a positive example and offering insights on effectively implementing CPPPA, thus contributing to the program's success and enhancing overall community safety.

Upang maipagpatuloy ang pagpapatupad na ito bilang mga opisyal ng pulisya dapat kong gawin ang aking trabaho nang mabisa at tumpak. Tinutulungan ko sila sa pamamagitan ng magandang halimbawa at pagbibigay ng ganoong ideya kung paano ipatupad ang CPPPA (Participant 4 lines 332-333)

In order to continue this implementation as a police officer, doing the job effectively and accurately is a must. Helping them by setting a good example and giving them an idea of implementing CPPPA (Participant 4, lines 332-333).

He was asked what insights he could share with other police officers or stations regarding the effective implementation of CPPPA. In response, he emphasized the importance of clarity regarding the goals and mission of CPPPA to ensure effective implementation. Additionally, he stressed the necessity for public acceptance of CPPPA to prevent conflicts.

In general, ibabahagi ko na ang layunin at misyon ng CPPPA na ito ay malinaw upang maisakatuparan natin ang CPPPA nang mabisa at dapat ding tanggapin ng mga tao ang CPPPA upang hindi magdulot ng mga salungatan. "" (Participant 4 lines 337-339)

In general, the CPPPA's goal and mission must be clear in order for us to implement it effectively. The CPPPA must also be acceptable to people to prevent conflicts (Participant 4, lines 337-339).

Table 4. *Experiences, Coping and Insights of PNP Personnel in the Implementation of Crime Prevention Plans, Programs and Activities (CPPPA)*

Cluster Themes	Emergent Themes
Experiences	
Community Support Challenges.	Difficult to Implement
Overcoming Obstacles.	
Impact on Work.	
Fulfillment from Positive Outcomes.	
Satisfaction in Service.	
Personal Growth.	Happiness
Collaborative Efforts.	
Importance of Community Engagement.	Partnership with the Community
Mutual Benefit.	
Challenges	
Lack of Community Support.	
Emotional Impact.	Mistrust
Lack of Trust.	
Challenges in Implementation.	
Lack of External Support.	Lack of Support
Not interesting in supporting the program.	
Professional Identity.	
Emotional Impact.	Self-Image
Mentally Affected.	
Insights	
Alignment in Goals and Missions.	
Public Acceptance.	Communication
Clarity in Implementation.	
Diligent in execution of duties.	
Commitment to Program Success.	Obeying to Others
Leadership in Implementation.	
Personal Dedication.	
Setting Positive Examples.	Good Example
Offering Insights and Guidance.	

Discussion

This part discussed significant findings and a summary and conclusions from the themes that surfaced from data analysis. This qualitative case study aims to determine the implementation of a Crime prevention plan, programs, and activities (CPPPA) in the eyes of PNP Personnel, particularly in the SOCCSKSARGEN police station.

Four participants were involved in this qualitative study: Ford: Compass, Trigger One, and Parachute. All of them are PNP personnel and are assigned at the CPPPA in the SOCSARGEN Region.

Major Findings

After an in-depth analysis of the data gathered, the following findings were drawn:

Experiences of PNP personnel in implementing Crime Prevention Plans, Programs and Activities (CPPPA)

It was revealed that there were three (3) emergent themes in the experiences of the PNP personnel in implementing Crime Prevention Plans, Programs, and Activities (CPPPA). These themes are challenging to implement, as well as happiness and partnership with the community.

Difficult to Implement. This study revealed that these PNP personnel needed help in implementing the CPPPA. The participants mentioned their difficulties due to different circumstances, such as the number of people involved, taking time to impose the law, and the community needing to cooperate more.

Based on the participants' verbatim accounts, PNP employees needed help implementing the CPPPA. The participants have discussed their struggles due to several factors, including the volume of parties engaged, the time it takes to enact the legislation, and the community's inadequate cooperation.

Research states that by acting to affect their many causes, crime prevention techniques and tactics aim to lower the likelihood that crimes will occur, as well as their potentially negative impacts on people and society, including the fear of crime. However, as several police academics and executives have noted, enhancing police performance through innovation is frequently challenging. Police agencies are reluctant to change, and new initiatives like the CPPPA are sometimes complex for officers to implement. Surprisingly, the plans requiring the most significant modifications to current police procedures and organizational structures report the most significant implementation challenges (Kyprianides et al., 2022; Tilley & Laycock, 2018).

Thus, the above verbatim account of the participants suggests that implementing CPPPA can be difficult, especially if the community is reluctant to make changes.

Happiness. This study also revealed that the participants experienced happiness despite adversity. One participant had mixed feelings about the CPPPA implementation; he considered it tiring and worrisome but still found happiness. Because it is his chosen job, he conducts it with pride and respect. Implementing the CPPPA was complex for one participant, but he was delighted since it helped the town become more peaceful and orderly. The final participant noted that witnessing the community's support for the CPPPA made him happy to see it implemented because it reduced crimes.

A more significant concept of the good life of the police officers combines intense fulfillment with genuine empathy for others. It is mainly filled with positive emotions but also with regret and nostalgia. It argues that numerous values make up human life and that happiness is just one of them. Compassion, knowledge, generosity, insight, and creativity can sometimes only be developed via hardship since extreme circumstances can drive police personnel through the complex transformation process. A calm, carefree living is not enough to live a whole human life. As a result, these police personnel also need to develop—and developing sometimes hurts (Brown, 2019; White et al., 2022).

However, based on the findings, the participants' perceptions of happiness about working conditions and work differed when classified according to profile characteristics. Thus, participants' happiness levels vary according to workplace views (Sutrisno & Sunars, 2019).

Partnership with the Community. One participant in this study expressed satisfaction with the CPPPA's implementation since it reduced crime and was well-received by the community. He continued by saying that one of the tactics utilized to deal with crises around the nation is the implementation of the CPPPA. He also said that helping the program gives the community access to a fairer social and educational environment. It is also incredibly beneficial since, as one participant noted, CPPPA will lessen crime and foster relationships between police officers and the local community. However, one participant shared his unique experience with the numerous difficulties they overcame without community support.

In another study, the researcher found that sometimes, people in the community are afraid to call the police about illegal activity because the criminals may come back and kill the police informants. For instance, people in Tondo, Manila, were reluctant to report crimes to the police out of concern that they might be used as informants and assassinated. Since the community may act as a watchdog for the police and report any questionable activity, this stated that the police-community collaboration should reduce the lens of reducing crime (Cobbina-Dungy & Jones-Brown, 2021; Giwa, 2018).

Challenges encountered by the PNP personnel in implementing the CPA

Mistrust. Police efficacy and the legality of their operations can be improved by public trust in the police. Therefore, it relates to the national police's ability to offer fundamental public safety. Researchers state that trust also permits police legitimacy —' the assessment individuals make about the appropriateness of police activity and the institutions that employ and govern them. It does so through its premise of compassion, devotion, and a shared ethical framework. A greater likelihood of successful public cooperation with police exists when the public perceives police as legitimate (or trustworthy) (Johnson et al., 2022; Van Damme, 2021).

However, other researchers stated that one should take such trust seriously. Due to its highly dependent nature in the majority of social relationships, trust is weak. Its prevalence and existence rely upon several elements inside and outside police control. A deficit of trust

in the police is all too typical in highly divided, post-conflict, and post-authoritarian nations. Public Trust in the police is, however, typically problematic whenever there are clear signs of social instability and relative socioeconomic disparity (Johnson et al., 2022).

In this study, the participants' verbatim accounts revealed that they experienced mistrust. The notion that the PNP does not enjoy widespread support is the biggest obstacle for one participant. He continued by saying that when a community does not initially trust the police, it is tough to inspire them. Nevertheless, these law officials could deal with it by holding on to the hope that they might win the public's trust one day.

Lack of support. It will also be challenging to maintain trust when the police are ordered or decide to uphold laws not widely supported by the public. Police routinely required to uphold unpopular laws will gradually lose public support for their general obligations, and civil unrest and even rebellion may occur where laws are unpopular. This results in the seeming paradox that, over time, a weak police force with public support will be more successful than a strong police force without it (Anderson et al., 2022; Brower, 2021).

Based on the participants' verbatim experiences, the implementation issues they face are a need for more community cooperation with the police officers allocated in the municipality because people are scared to report such incidents that are happening in their regions. Other participants agreed with this assertion.

Furthermore, community policing is both a method and a concept. It aims to promote organizational strategies that support the systematic use of partnership and problem-solving techniques to quickly address public safety issues, such as crime, social disorder, and fear. Community involvement as a strategy is about establishing a partnership between various stakeholders, such as the police, citizens, and other service providers, to reduce the crime rate in affected areas (Girardi, 2022).

Self-Image. The policeman's reputation in the community nowadays is poor. The media helped this perception, frequently emphasizing how poorly police officers were perceived. Police organizations are open to public scrutiny; therefore, any errors committed by their staff are frequently condemned. Although the performance of the police could not be affected by these images, their impact must be taken into account. The community needs to conduct additional research into the actual circumstances to make assumptions based on these images and the information provided by media professionals (Agwanwo & Okorie, 2021; Nurmisyta et al., 2021; Vukovic, 2022).

Additionally, even though police service delivery and communication have improved, ongoing issues between the police and the community continue to exist. The police culture is continually evolving, and one shift is the greater focus on morality and integrity concerns. The community's perspective can also affect how the public views the police. It contains opinions about how kind and impartial the police are. An effective police-community relationship has a beneficial effect as well. This factor is crucial in winning the community's support (Huihuang, 2022; Rondina, 2018).

The above literature was supported by the verbatim accounts of the participants on their claim about the self-image of a police officer. The community's suspicion of police officers damaged the participants' mental and emotional well-being since they were unable to convince others of the CPPPA's ability to assist society in avoiding crime, notwithstanding their lack of interest in doing so. Meanwhile, another participant openly admitted that those difficulties made him feel less self-assured and confident. As a result, he began to doubt his suitability to hold a position of responsibility.

Insights of PNP personnel in the implementation of Crime Prevention Plans, Programs and Activities (CPPPA)

Communication. Police personnel need excellent communication skills to serve the public; communication is crucial in today's society. Ineffective listening or speaking skills could cause a misconception. In both their personal lives and professional careers, police officers depend heavily on communication. Authorities can better control the evidence by questioning witnesses and suspects and obtaining information. As a result, they can make prompt, well-informed judgments. Only through developing their social and professional communication skills will police officers be able to work effectively behind the scenes and feel at ease with the public (Dolamore et al., 2022).

Additionally, the public reacts to officers; effective communication is crucial for police officers to deal with the public effectively. All of these actions allow cops to influence how the public perceives them. Lack of these crucial communication abilities causes misunderstandings, leaves an officer unsure of how to continue, and discourages those needing police aid. Officers must also consider how communication may influence how a community responds. These qualities are crucial for the best police job. Experience has shown that when police officers treat individuals nicely, they respond with more composure and cooperation. Therefore, effective communication is essential to making police officers' tasks more straightforward and fulfilling (Farmer & Copenhaver, 2021).

Obeying the Orders. Police officers value life and freedom because they are police officers. They are considerate, welcoming, and compassionate, treating everyone with respect. We expect responsibility, consistency, fairness, and honesty in discharging our obligations because the principles of justice govern them. They uphold the highest ethical standards and are proud of their department. They uphold the most significant level of education in our sector and are dedicated to doing their jobs well.

Additionally, they preserve moral fortitude and mental toughness to face challenges and think pretty. In peril or adversity, they unfailingly support their fellow officers. Because job responsibilities include all necessary chores, these police personnel are forced to follow the law (Bloksgaard & Prieur, 2021; Oleksii et al., 2021).

The participant claims that the wisdom they can impart is to carry out whatever duties the authorities assign by the PNP regulations. A different participant made the claim. According to him, following instructions and implementing the program equitably for the community's concerned citizens, such as conducting PCR to regain the community's faith in the PNP, is essential to properly executing the CPPPA. The participants also mentioned that it is vital to concentrate on the CPPPA's objectives and purpose since doing so will help to minimize crime and advance peace.

Good Example. Today's law enforcement authorities are dealing with one of the most turbulent periods in policing. On a broad scale, law enforcement institutions are under growing pressure to review their procedures while juggling a terrain shifting in terms of culture, society, and technology. On a personal level, new expectations about what it means to be an officer and how they want to be led are being brought into the field by police officers themselves (Ghavami et al., 2021).

In this study, the participants accounted that as police personnel, they should become a role model. One participant discovered that implementing the CPPPA into practice will reduce crime rates overall. He continued that they must also be an excellent example to others and must love what they do. Another attendee stressed that the PNP personnel's ability to administer and overcome obstacles will determine how successfully the program is implemented. They must set a positive example for the neighborhood to win its support and regain its trust. The last participant advised other PNP offices to preserve morality and abstain from conduct that would harm the PNP's reputation.

Additionally, law enforcement professionals should have a few qualities. These characteristics influence their level of professionalism, how people perceive their level of safety, how suspects behave around them, and even how their careers will develop in the future. Some of the most crucial character traits are reported by police officers who are currently on the force (Muller et al., 2021).

Lastly, it is critical to consider the community's receptive character and the expectation that police officers everywhere behave as role models. This aspect of the work is crucial since the public will frequently observe the police and be a prominent presence in the neighborhood. In addition, most law enforcement officers interact with the public infrequently and are only briefly visible to the general public (e.g., when driving by in a patrol car or directing traffic); however, young people may frequently interact with school police officers over several years. Thus, in one instance, an officer's lousy judgment may be circulated in the school and enhanced with each account of the incident since schools are closed environments where students are familiar with their peers and spend a significant amount of time chatting (Montes et al., 2021; Nijjar, 2021).

Comparison of Findings with Existing Studies

Experiences of PNP personnel in implementing Crime Prevention Plans, Programs, and Activities (CPPPA). Techniques and strategies for preventing crimes lessen the possibility that they will happen, as well as their potentially detrimental effects on people and society, including the dread of crime. However, as various scholars and executives in the police department have noticed, improving police performance through innovation is typically tricky. Police departments are highly resistant to change, and it can be challenging for officers to put innovative programs like the CPPPA into practice. Remarkably, the proposals reporting the most implementation difficulties call for the most dramatic changes to present police practices and organizational structures (Kyprianides et al., 2022; Tilley & Laycock, 2018).

This study also revealed that the participants experienced happiness despite adversity. One participant had mixed feelings about the CPPPA implementation; he considered it tiring but still found happiness. This more general idea of a satisfying life for police officers combines a deep sense of fulfillment with sincere compassion for others. It is mainly composed of positive feelings but also seasoned with remorse and sadness. It makes the case that pleasure is only one of many qualities that go into creating a human existence. Only harsh circumstances can occasionally motivate police officers to undergo the challenging change process. Therefore, qualities like compassion, wisdom, generosity, insight, and creativity may occasionally only be acquired via adversity. Living a tranquil, carefree life is insufficient for a whole human existence. Therefore, these police officers also need to grow, which sometimes hurts (Brown, 2019; White et al., 2022).

However, based on the findings of participants' perceptions of happiness about working conditions and work itself, when classified according to profile characteristics, differed. Thus, participants' happiness levels vary according to workplace views (Sutrisno & Sunarsi, 2019).

In a different study, it was discovered that occasionally, residents are reluctant to report unlawful activities to the police for fear that the offenders may return and murder the police informants. For instance, citizens in Tondo, Manila, reportedly hesitated to report crimes to the police out of fear that they would be employed as informants and killed. This research suggested that the police-community partnership should be enhanced to lower crime since the community may serve as a watchdog for the police and report any dubious activities (Cobbina-Dungy & Jones-Brown, 2021; Giwa, 2018).

Challenges encountered by the PNP personnel in implementing the CPPPA. Public Trust in the police may enhance both their effectiveness and the legitimacy of their actions. As a result, it concerns the national police's capacity to provide essential public safety. It also enables police legitimacy — the judgments that regular people make on the suitability of police activities and the organizations that employ and oversee them. It accomplishes it based on its foundation of compassion, dedication, and a standard ethical code. When

the public views police as genuine (or trustworthy), there is a higher possibility that collaboration between police and the public will be successful (Johnson et al., 2022; Van Damme, 2021).

However, research states that confidence should not be taken for granted. Most social interactions could be stronger since trust dramatically depends on them. Its frequency and existence depend on many factors that are both under and independent of police control. In highly polarized, post-conflict, and post-authoritarian countries, there is all too often a lack of faith in the police. However, when there is apparent social unrest and relative socioeconomic disparities, the public's faith in the police is frequently an issue (Johnson et al., 2022).

Moreover, when the police are asked to enforce laws that the public does not generally agree with, or when they choose to do so, it will be challenging to preserve faith in the police. There may be social unrest and even insurrection in areas where laws are unpopular. Officers frequently obliged to enforce unpopular laws may progressively lose public support for their general responsibilities. Thus, it appears paradoxical that a weak police force with public support will eventually be more effective than a significant police force without it (Anderson et al., 2022; Brower, 2021).

In addition, community enforcement is both a concept and a technique. It strives to advance organizational tactics that encourage the methodical application of collaboration and problem-solving methods to swiftly handle pressing public safety challenges, including crime, social disturbance, and terror. To lower the crime rate in impacted regions, community participation as a technique entails forging a relationship between multiple stakeholders, including the police, residents, and other service providers (Girardi, 2022)

Consequently, the police officer has a bad reputation in the neighborhood. The media, which constantly highlighted how negatively people viewed police personnel, contributed to this attitude. Since police agencies are subject to public inspection, any mistakes made by their employees are widely denounced. Although these photographs could not influence the police's performance, their impact must be considered. The community made inferences based on these photographs and the information supplied by media professionals without investigating the facts (Agwanwo & Okorie, 2021; Nurnisya et al., 2021; Vukovic, 2022).

Furthermore, despite improvements in communication and service delivery, there are still persistent problems between the police and the community. One recent change in the police culture is emphasizing morals and integrity issues. How the public sees the police also depends on their point of view. It offers viewpoints on the fairness and objectivity of the police. Additionally, a strong police-community partnership is advantageous. This aspect is vital to gaining the community's support (Huihuang, 2022; Rondina, 2018).

Insights of PNP personnel in implementing Crime Prevention Plans, Programs and Activities (CPPPA). Communication is critical in today's culture since police officers must have excellent communication skills to serve the public. A misunderstanding could result from poor speech or listening abilities. The ability to communicate is a crucial skill for police officers in both their personal and professional lives. Authorities are better equipped to manage the evidence when interrogating witnesses and suspects and gathering information. As a result, they can make quick, educated decisions. Police officers can only function well behind the scenes and be at ease with the public by improving their social and professional communication skills (Dolamore et al., 2022).

Additionally, effective communication is essential for police officers to engage with the public efficiently because it impacts how people react to cops. All of these behaviors can influence the public's perception of police officers. Lack of these vital communication skills results in miscommunications, leaving an officer unclear on how to proceed, and demoralizes persons needing police assistance. Police must also consider how a community's response may be influenced by communication. These characteristics are essential for the ideal policy position. People behave more calmly and cooperatively when police officers treat them correctly, according to experience. Therefore, efficient communication is crucial to simplifying and enhancing the duties of police personnel (Farmer & Copenhaver, 2021).

Moreover, it was found that while they work in law enforcement, police officers respect human life and freedom. They treat everyone with respect and are courteous, hospitable, and inviting. Because the rules of justice control them and respect the most significant ethical standards, they demand accountability, consistency, fairness, and honesty in fulfilling the commitments and being pleased with their division. They uphold the highest standard of education in our industry and are committed to carrying out their duties effectively. They also retain the moral fortitude and mental courage to overcome obstacles and reason honestly. They always stand by their fellow officers whether they are in danger or facing difficulties. These police officers are compelled to uphold the law since their jobs require them to do all relevant duties (Oleksii et al., 2021).

Furthermore, today's law enforcement officials face one of the most challenging eras in police history. On a large scale, law enforcement agencies are dealing with demand to assess their practices as they navigate a constantly changing social, technological, and cultural landscape. On a personal level, police officers are bringing new standards of what it means to be an officer and how they want to be led into the field (Ghavami et al., 2021).

On the other hand, law enforcement professionals need to possess a few traits. These traits influence their degree of professionalism, others' perception of their level of safety around them, suspects' responses around them, and even their career prospects in the future. According to police officers serving on the force, these are some of the most crucial character qualities (Muller et al., 2021).

Conclusion

The findings of this study provided valuable insights into the experiences, challenges, and realizations of PNP personnel involved in implementing Crime Prevention Plans, Programs, and Activities (CPPPA). The study aimed to understand the perspectives of PNP staff members, leading to the emergence of themes such as challenging implementation, happiness, and community partnership. Additionally, the study shed light on the difficulties faced by PNP staff in executing CPPPA, highlighting themes of mistrust, a lack of support, and self-image. Furthermore, the study sought the opinions of PNP staff on effective strategies for CPPPA implementation, revealing themes of communication, adherence to orders, and setting a positive example.

In line with the study's findings, strong police-community ties are crucial in reducing crime rates. The research demonstrated that these collaborations contributed to the city's crime rate decline. However, certain obstacles, such as distrust, lack of support, and self-image issues, limit the success of police-community collaborations. In addressing these challenges, the study suggests prioritizing police service resources, establishing legislative support for community policing tactics, and improving trust and community engagement.

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